

symbionts, *A. azollae* (AS-K₄) and (AS-S₁), and two free-living blue-green algae, *Anabaena* sp. (FL) and *Nostoc* sp. (FL), in calcium alginate on ammonia excretion and its influence on the growth of IR64 rice seedlings.

These N₂-fixing algal cultures were grown in IRRI N-free liquid medium for 2 wk in a growth room at 26 ± 1°C with 2000-3000 lux light intensity.

Suspensions were prepared from these cultures and mixed with an equal volume of calcium alginate aqueous solution (2.4%). The N content before immobilization in alginate was 2.96% for AS-K₄, 2.91% for AS-S₁, 3.14% for *Anabaena* sp., and 3.64% for *Nostoc* sp. Using a 10-ml pipette, the mixture of algal suspension in calcium alginate was added drop by drop to a solution containing 50 mM calcium chloride, resulting in the formation of round beads (Fig. 1). The algal beads were washed thoroughly, set on IRRI N-free medium, and incubated under the same growth room condition as the culture. Using Nessler's reagent method, we then measured ammonia excretion from the filtrate of the medium in which the algal beads had been maintained for 2 wk.

Nostoc sp., *A. azollae* (AS-K₄), *A. azollae* (AS-S₁), and *Anabaena* excreted 52.57, 34.28, 27.40, and 19.14 µg ammonia/m per 100 ml medium, respectively.

Forty IR64 rice seedlings that had been raised in sterile sand culture were maintained in a plastic cup. They were inoculated with 80 immobilized alginate algal beads (about 4,500 algal cells/algal bead). Sterile water was added and kept at a depth of 2.5 cm for 5 wk under controlled conditions. The seedlings were then carefully pulled out. Root, shoot growth, fresh biomass, and N

2. Effect of alginate-immobilized algal symbionts of azolla and free-living blue-green algae on growth of IR64 rice seedlings.

content were all significantly increased when plants were inoculated with alginate-immobilized algal beads. Inoculation with immobilized algal beads significantly increased the N content in IR64 rice seedlings over the control. N content ranged from .528% (*A. azollae* [AS-S₁]) to .588% (*Nostoc* [FL]) in the immobilized algal inoculated plants, and was .392% in the

control. Algal beads immobilized with *Nostoc* sp. produced the best seedling growth (Fig. 2).

The results showed that the immobilized algal symbionts of Azolla and free-living blue-green algae can continuously excrete ammonia that can be absorbed by rice seedlings and used in their growth. The cost of alginate beads at 5 kg/ha is \$7.5. □

Integrated pest management—diseases

Antagonistic Soil bacteria for biological control of rice sheath blight (ShB) disease

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We explored the possibility of using antagonistic soil bacteria for biological control of ShB caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn. We isolated bacteria from samples collected from areas covering four administrative divisions in Bangladesh. We tested 523 bacteria by placing two organisms in the plate

medium (dual culture method); 19.3% were antagonistic to varying degrees toward *R. solani* in vitro. Among these, 15% were fluorescent and 85% were nonfluorescent types.

Six bacteria were further tested for antagonism by dual culture and sclerotia dipping methods (Table 1). Isolate IS-

241 produced the maximum zone of inhibition on potato dextrose agar (PDA) and inhibited germination of sclerotia. The sclerotia treated with bacteria failed to produce symptoms on cut leaves of rice. The sclerotia were further tested in vitro through seed treatment and foliar spray.

For seed treatment, surface-sterilized BR1 seeds were soaked overnight in the bacterial suspension (10^8 colony-forming units [cfu]/ml) and sown in trays, along with a control, in the greenhouse. Shoot length was measured after 15 d.

Seedlings were transplanted into pots and in the field. Plants at booting stage were inoculated with *R. solani* (10-d-old culture on rice straw).

For the foliar spray treatment, rice cultivars BR1 and BR11 were planted in the field during 1990 aus (Apr-Jul) and transplanted aman (Jul-Nov) seasons, respectively. In both seasons the plants were inoculated with *R. solani* at booting stage, and then sprayed with bacteria (10^8 cfu/ml) 3 d later. We measured disease development as percentage of diseased sheath and leaf area at maturity for both treatments.

Whether applied as seed treatment or foliar spray, the isolates all increased seedling height and reduced total sheath and leaf area infected with ShB. IS-241

Table 1. Cultural characteristics and activity of 6 antagonistic bacteria against *R. solani*.

Strain	Cultural characteristics				Antagonistic activity			
	Colony type	Color	Growth type	Slime production ^a	Reaction to UV light ^b	Zone of inhibition on PDA (mm)	Germination of sclerotia ^c (%)	Sclerotia producing ShB symptom ^d (%)
IS-135	Irregular	Creamy	Fast	-	fl	2.0	83	17
IS-158	Round	Yellowish	Slow	+	fl	5.8	50	17
IS-241	Round	Dull white	Very slow	-	nfl	8.1	0	0
IS-243	Irregular	Reddish	Fast	-	nfl	3.3	50	17
IS-245	Round	Whitish	Fast	-	nfl	3.0	100	42
IS-315	Wavy margin	Dull white	Slow	-	nfl	3.0	100	58
Control	-	-	-	-	-	0.0	100	100

^a+ = produces slime, - = does not produce slime. ^bfl = fluorescent, nfl = nonfluorescent. ^cTested after dipping the sclerotia in bacterial suspension (10^8 CFU/ml). ^dSclerotia were inoculated on cut leaves of rice in vitro for germination and infection.

Table 2. Effect of seed treatment and foliar spray with antagonistic bacteria on management of rice ShB.^a

Strain	Seed treatment			Foliar spray	
	Seedling shoot length (cm)	Diseased sheath and leaf area (%)		Diseased sheath and leaf area (%)	
		Pot	Field	Aus 1990	T. aman 1990
IS-135	24.1	6.1	14.8	8.9	4.4
IS-158	23.0	8.0	25.1	9.0	4.8
IS-241	25.7	6.3	15.3	9.7	4.0
IS-243	23.8	9.9	27.0	11.0	4.5
IS-245	23.5	9.6	16.7	9.9	4.3
IS-315	23.3	9.6	19.0	9.0	5.2
Control	22.7	10.3	24.7	13.2	8.3

^aAll figures are means of 3 replications. ShB development was measured as percent sheath and leaf area infected at maturity.

was most effective against ShB (Table 2). This bacterium was isolated from

lowland soil collected from Nandail, Kishoreganj. □

A new inoculation technique for neck blast (BI) on in vitro rice panicles

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Rice B1, caused by *Pyricularia grisea*, is a serious rice disease. Of its two recognized phases, neck B1 is often more destructive than leaf BI in the field. Leaf B1 is generally positively correlated with neck B1. Some varieties, however, are exceptions to this general relationship and therefore improved

methods are required for neck B1 testing. We studied a new technique for inoculating rice plants with the neck B1 pathogen for use in resistance screening.

Panicles of six varieties with varying degrees of susceptibility to B1 were excised 0-10 d after heading. The boot leaf and one culm node were retained. The in vitro panicles with boot leaf were placed in a glass tube containing 20 ml water, which was changed every 48 h.

We used a brush to smear panicles with a mixture of $1-2 \times 10^5$ conidia/ml, suspended in 1-2% carboxymethyl cellulose. These inoculated panicles were incubated inside a dew chamber for 24 h at 26-

